

*Cross-sectoral planning decision-making
platform to foster climate action*

Summary results of Valle d'Aosta case study (CS4)

Policy Brief

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H2020-LC-GD-2020-2: LC-GD-9-2-2020. Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation

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Rethinking Valle D'Aosta in a changing climate

Key findings

- The stakeholder-based co-creation approach effectively identified priorities and shared solutions.
- Climate change will intensify risks through glacier retreat, rising temperatures, and rainfall variability, leading to more droughts and localized water scarcity.
- Land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) such as sustainable grassland management, wetland restoration, and alpine ecosystem protection can reduce climate risks.
- Integrated water management is essential to balance agricultural, hydropower, tourism, and household demands for long-term resource security.
- Conserving primary forests and regenerating degraded land will enhance ecosystem services, reduce soil erosion, and support regional attractiveness.
- Training, technical capacity, and infrastructure investments are needed to modernize hydropower, expand renewables, and strengthen system flexibility while protecting alpine ecosystems.
- Stakeholder perspectives and local knowledge must guide decision-making to ensure transparent, inclusive, and widely accepted climate policies.

Keywords: Valle D'Aosta; land-use; LAMS; water security; tourism; forest; energy; system dynamics; adaptation; mitigation; implementation climate solutions

Executive Summary

The Valle D'Aosta, located in northwestern Italy, is the country's smallest and least densely populated region, embedded in the Alpine system and bordering both France and Switzerland. Its economy relies on hydropower production, alpine tourism, and traditional agriculture and livestock farming that sustain rural communities and cultural landscapes. Stakeholders highlighted climate pressures, glacier retreat, uneven precipitation, hotter summers, and increasing droughts, that threaten water availability, energy reliability, agricultural productivity, and the long-term attractiveness of mountain tourism. This policy brief distills stakeholder-selected **land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS)** that keep development within ecosystem limits while advancing decarbonisation.

Source: <https://pixabay.com/>

It outlines practical options to strengthen integrated water management, promote climate-resilient farming and livestock systems, diversify the tourism model, and ensure a balanced renewable energy expansion in a fragile alpine environment. The brief targets regional policymakers, local authorities, farmers' associations, tourism operators, and energy planners.

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Background & Policy Context

Climate change is a risk multiplier that can exacerbate existing risks and crises through the interaction between climatic and non-climatic drivers. This includes land use change, which plays a crucial role in achieving the ambitious targets for climate resilience and climate neutrality in the European Union (EU) by 2050, as outlined in the framework of the EU Green Deal strategy ([Chiriaco et al., 2025](#)). The RethinkAction project supports the objectives of the EU Green Deal. In this context, the RethinkAction (H2020) project co-develops land-use-based adaptation and mitigation solutions (LAMS) with stakeholders across six EU case studies to reduce land-use-based emissions from various land-use types.

¹ Chiriaco, M.V. et al. (2025). A catalogue of land-based adaptation and mitigation solutions to tackle climate change. *Sci Data* 12, 166 [[doi](#)].

High-resolution land use map of the *Valle d'Aosta*. Source: RethinkAction project

The Valle D'Aosta region is one of these six case studies that also explored different LAMS to complement its contribution to EU Green Deal target.

The economy of Valle d'Aosta relies mainly on services, with tourism as a key driver, alongside industry linked to hydropower and a smaller but vital agricultural sector. It depends on ecosystem services such as water availability, fertile soils and preserved alpine landscapes. Policies must balance economic development with ecological limits while advancing decarbonisation and climate resilience.

Air temperature for historical period (1985-2014). Source: [RethinkAction Platform](#)

Climate & Geographic Focus for LAMS

Located in the heart of the Alps and surrounded by peaks such as Mont Blanc, the Matterhorn, Monte Rosa and Gran Paradiso, the Valle d'Aosta has a predominantly alpine climate, with long, cold winters and significant variations between valley floors and higher altitudes. The main valley is relatively dry due to limited ventilation, while side valleys show diverse microclimates that support specialized wine-growing areas. Agriculture depends on irrigation systems, historically managed through the Rûs canals, to compensate for scarce rainfall. Livestock grazing and grasslands remain critical for maintaining rural economies and landscapes. Seasonal peaks in tourism increase pressure on water resources, while hydropower, a central energy source, faces growing risks from glacier retreat and changing river flows. Solar and wind resources offer complementary opportunities to diversify the regional energy mix, but must be balanced against the fragile alpine environment.

Land-based Adaptation and Mitigation Solutions (LAMS) were prioritized by stakeholders and are central to ensure that Valle d’Aosta remains productive, climate-resilient, and ecologically sustainable.

Bridging Science and Society for Climate-Resilience Development

RethinkAction used state-of-the-art tools to connect climate scenarios with land-use decisions and policy options. The applied methodology combined climate modelling, land-use analysis, stakeholder engagement, and System Dynamics modelling to co-design actionable pathways. A participatory, multi-scale approach was applied, combining quantitative modelling with multiple stakeholder co-creation workshops across six case studies to evaluate different future alternatives.

Data collection, modelling, and policy analysis were carried out. A total of five basic *Essential Climate Variables* (Basic-ECVs) and 24 Derived-ECVs were downscaled to assess future exposures, followed by the identification of suitable LAMS based on both a literature review and multicriteria analysis, and their suitability at the local scale. Local stakeholders were involved in the evaluation of the potential risks across sectors through impact chains and the selection of potential packages of solutions, along with the main potential drivers and barriers of the region.

Local Workshop in Valle d’Aosta (May 2024): Stakeholder developing an impact chain. Source: RethinkAction project.

The used Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs) were SSP1-2.6 (with lower emissions), SSP2-4.5 (with mid-range emissions) and SSP5-8.5 (highest emissions)

Translating Data into Action

In the coming decades, Valle d’Aosta is expected to face a marked reduction in snow cover, with shorter snow duration particularly in valley floors and mid-mountain areas. By mid-century, snow days could decrease by 15–20 at 2000 m and up to 45 days at lower altitudes, while winter snowfall may fall by 25–45% overall. These reductions will translate into a 20–30% loss of water reserves stored in snow and an earlier melting period of around one month, extending to two months under the most pessimistic climate scenario. Such changes will reduce water availability for agriculture, hydropower, and ecosystems, while also threatening winter tourism and increasing exposure to natural hazards such as landslides and flash floods. By the end of the century, average temperatures in Valle d’Aosta are projected to rise significantly, with more frequent heatwaves and a marked reduction in days with temperatures below freezing. These shifts will intensify evapotranspiration, reduce soil moisture, and increase thermal stress on both ecosystems and communities. Glaciers are expected to retreat rapidly, with many below 3,000–3,500 m disappearing entirely, leading to substantial landscape change, biodiversity loss, and new natural hazards. Altered seasonality of river flows and reduced summer water balance will further stress agriculture, hydropower, and water security across the region.

Anomalies of monthly precipitation for Valle d’Aosta comparing the period 2071-2100 to the historical period (1985 - 2015) for SSP 1.2.6, 2.4.5 and 5.8.5. Source: RethinkAction project.

Tourism in Valle d’Aosta is increasingly exposed to climate risks, from reduced snow cover and heatwaves to ecosystem degradation and water scarcity, threatening both winter sports and summer outdoor activities. The energy sector, largely dependent on hydropower, must adapt to fluctuating river flows while integrating more solar and wind generation, ensuring system flexibility and ecological safeguards in a fragile alpine environment.

Considering the most relevant risks, stakeholders had chosen specific LAMS for tourism, energy and agriculture sectors. The LAMS displayed are “Soil management in grassland”, “Hydropower deployment” and “Protecting and promoting forest natural encroachment”.

Local SD Model – Simulation Results

Solar PV installed in Valle d’Aosta, under low, medium and high level of implementation intensity, for SSP2 scenario.

Stakeholder-Chosen LAMS

Soil management in grassland

Hydropower deployment

Protection of primary forests

Conclusions

Valle d’Aosta faces the dual challenge of safeguarding its unique alpine environment while securing the foundations of its economy, built on tourism, hydropower, and agriculture. Strengthening resilience means moving beyond sectoral measures and adopting integrated strategies that link water governance, land management, and renewable energy deployment. Protecting forests, maintaining productive grasslands, and supporting traditional farming systems are essential to sustain ecosystem services and rural communities. At the same time, diversifying tourism models and modernizing energy infrastructure must be pursued with ecological safeguards and community acceptance. Achieving these goals requires coordinated policies, transparent data, and the active involvement of local actors, ensuring that adaptation and mitigation strategies reinforce each other. With this approach, Valle d’Aosta can balance economic vitality with environmental stewardship and secure a sustainable future for its people and landscapes.

The key outcomes described in this brief are available in the Resources section of the [RethinkAction website](#) and in the [RethinkAction platform](#).

² Barilari, S. et al. (2025). Climate Risk and Vulnerability Assessment in the Province of Almeria (Spain) Under Different Climate Change Scenarios. *Climate*, 13(7), 141. [doi]

Impact chains were used to analyse these complex vulnerable conditions, considering all the factors involved. They are a tool that considers all the risk components and synthesizes the complex connections between them. They were quantified in the project following ([Barilari et al., 2025²](#)) and the results are available in the [RethinkAction platform](#). These changes create multiple interconnected risks for the Valle D’Aosta. Two **impact chains** were developed to describe the risks in each sector: *Risk of increasing temperatures affecting hydropower generation (Energy)*; *Risk of loss of attractiveness due to snow variation as consequence of climate change (Winter Tourism)*.

Quantified risk through Impact Chains in Valle D’Aosta for tourism sector. Source: RethinkAction project.

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